

STUDY TECHNOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF DRY EXTRACT "ANTIOXIM"

F.B.Ismailova., X.M.Yunusova.

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent city, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: fz.ismailova555@gmail.com, tel: (99)816-27-70

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10681791>

Annotation: The study of domestic medicinal plants as a source of biologically active substances makes it possible to obtain new medicinal preparations and introduce them into medical practice. It is necessary that all medicinal plants have a complex effect, are easy to master, do not have contraindications and side effects. According to the scientific literature, the proportion of herbal preparations is about 90%, their high physiological activity depends on the harmonious combination and interaction of biologically active substances contained in the preparations used. Therefore, plants remain an indispensable source of obtaining drugs of various directions.

In this study, the results of the study of physico-chemical technological peculiarities of dry extract obtained on the basis of a three-component plant composition are presented.

Key words: medicinal plant, technological properties, active substances, specification.

The purpose of the study: In order to optimize production, it is important to study the relationship between the physico-chemical and technological properties of materials, to choose the optimal excipients and to base their process flow on obtaining drug forms Development of a technology for obtaining a dry extract from collection of plant "Antioxim".

Method and Methods: Studying the physico-chemical properties of the recommended dry extract showed that the extracts are dry, hygroscopic, light yellow-brown powders with a specific smell, mass loss during drying is 3.51%, heavy metals is 0.0089, the moisture content of the dry extract was determined by the device of the Japanese company "Kett" to be 9.58%, the quantitative content of biologically active substances is 95.99%. Further study of the technological properties of the dry extract showed that it is necessary in the development of the technology of solid dosage forms.

Results: The results of the study of the physical and chemical properties of the recommended dry extract are presented in the table below.

Specification	Results
Appearance	Dry extracts, hygroscopic, amorphous powder, light yellowish-brown color, with a specific odor.
Authenticity	correspond
Dry residue of dried mass, %	3,51
Heavy metals, %	0,0089 kam
Humidity, %	9,58
Microbiological purity	correspond
Quantitative composition, %	95,99

Conclusion: Due to the fact that the dry extract is characterized by hygroscopicity, low solubility, it is impossible to obtain a granule (for example, for Tablet preparation, for capsule dosage forms) without the introduction of auxiliary substances in improving the technological

properties of the mass. According to the results of the dry extract" antioxidant " showed that it is very hygroscopic, when preparing granules, it is necessary to choose auxiliary substances from it (tablet or capsule dosage form based on Granules).

References:

1. State Pharmacopoeia Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan.Vol. I, Tashkent. 2021. - P. 418.
2. Methodological guidelines in the Manual for the experimental (preclinical) study of new pharmacological substances. Under the general editorship of corresponding member of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Professor R. U. KHABRIEV. The second edition, revised and supplemented/. M.: - 2005. - M.: JSC "Publishing House "Medicine", 2005.-p. 830
3. Akopov I. E. The most important domestic medicinal plants and their use: a reference book - Tashkent: Medicine, 1990. p-444.
4. Ismailova F.B., Yunusova Kh.M.// Antioxidant drug in local pharmaceutical market analysis of the nomenclature of instruments//. VII. Kazakh state pharmaceutical academy» Republican scientific journal, Vestnik #4(94), 2021, volume IV. -P. 50-51.